

DEVELOPMENT OF PERFORMANCE STYLE SKILLS IN INSTRUMENTAL PERFORMANCE (ON THE EXAMPLE OF THE ACCORDION)

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Abstract: This article discusses the issues of forming and developing performance style skills in the process of playing an instrument, in particular, in playing the accordion. Performance style is a harmonious manifestation of the performer's technical skills, means of expression, individual approach to the text of the work, and aesthetic taste. The study analyzes the role of technical and expressive means inherent in accordion performance, including notation, register change, dynamic transitions, legato and staccato methods. The article also provides methodological recommendations for forming a performance style based on the musical analysis of accordion works. Pedagogical methods aimed at developing the student's individual creativity, conscious understanding of musical expression, and ensuring freedom on stage are of great importance in the approach. The results of the study serve to effectively organize practical classes in accordion performance and improve the professional training of students.

Keywords: accordion, performance style, performance skills, technical skills, means of expression, musical analysis, register, dynamic transition, legato, staccato, stage culture.

Introduction.

The art of playing an instrument is one of the most diverse and vital manifestations of musical expression. It requires not only technical skill, but also a perfect harmony of creative thinking, musical awareness and aesthetic taste. Especially on an instrument with such a complex structure as the accordion, achieving a high level of performance art is directly related to the formation of the performer's individual approach to the musical text and the skills of effectively using stylistic means of expression.

Accordion performance is not only the perfection of technical movements, but also the art of revealing the spiritual and aesthetic essence of the work, feeling the inner tone of each phrase during performance, expressing them through dynamic and timbre changes. Such an approach, in turn, requires the

development of performance style skills. Performance style is the personal approach of the performer, the conscious choice of technical and musical means of expression, their combination based on aesthetic criteria. Therefore, one of the important criteria determining the professional maturity of an accordion player is his possession of a performance style and knowledge of the ways to form it.

In recent years, special attention has been paid to improving the performance culture in the music education system, developing independent performance skills in students and pupils, and harmoniously forming technical and expressive skills. However, in practical experience, approaches in this regard are often limited only to technique, note reading and accuracy. This neglects the deep musical content of the performing art and the uniqueness of the means of expression. This article is of urgent importance in this regard. It analyzes the components of the performance style in accordion playing, the stages of their development, pedagogical approaches and methodological recommendations on a scientific basis. Also, factors such as musical analysis, understanding of the character of the work, stage culture, and psychological preparation are analyzed in the formation of performance style. The main purpose of the article is to identify modern pedagogical approaches to the formation of performance style in instrumental performance, in particular, accordion performance, and to develop scientific and methodological recommendations aimed at their application in practice.

Literature analysis:

The analysis of scientific and methodological literature on the formation of performance style skills in instrumental performance, in particular, accordion art, shows that research in this area is carried out on the basis of a wide range of approaches.

First of all, the methodological works of such Russian pedagogues as O. V. Yastrebova, A. A. Kostin, V. V. Bolotin on the activities of an accordion teacher are noteworthy. In particular, O. V. Yastrebova's work "The Art of Bayan Performance" describes in detail the ways to ensure the harmony of performance technique and means of expression. The author emphasizes that musical phrasing, articulation, register changes and specific types of dynamics play an important role in the formation of the performance style.

V. Bolotin, on the other hand, justifies the choice of repertoire as an important factor in the formation of the performance style. According to him, the repertoire, which includes works by composers of different periods, forms not

only technical skills, but also the ability to creatively observe, feel the environment and create a musical image.

A number of methodological manuals written by Uzbek teachers, for example, in the works of D. Urazmetov, M. Izzatullayev and N. Akhmedov, emphasize national traditions of accordion performance. These writers emphasize the need to develop national means of expression in students through exercises based on Uzbek folk melodies. Also, the formation of national musical thinking and aesthetic worldview in students by forming the performance style on the basis of national musical materials is of great importance.

The theoretical works of B. I. Asafyev, L. Mazel and M. Aranovsky on musical thinking and expression reveal the aesthetic and musical essence of the general performance style. They interpret the art of performance not only as a set of technical skills, but also as a means of spiritual and cultural expression.

Modern sources, in particular, articles on the organization of instrumental education based on interactive technologies, highlight the possibilities of ICT tools, virtual classes, audio-visual analysis and distance pedagogy in the development of performance skills. This indicates the need for flexible and student-oriented approaches to the current educational process.

Scientific articles also deeply analyze the psychological aspects of the performance style - namely, stage culture, managing excitement during performance, and developing internal intonational hearing. Such psychopedagogical approaches serve the personal development of the accordion player. Literature analysis shows that the development of performance skills requires multifaceted approaches, the harmonious use of technical and expressive means, as well as pedagogical methods focused on the individual. In particular, the formation of these skills on such a wide-ranging instrument as the accordion requires a unique step-by-step methodology and artistic and aesthetic analysis.

The accordion is not only a source of sounds, but also a means of musical expression, emotion and artistic thinking. Each melody, each musical phrase performed with it is not only a reflection of the composer's thought, but also reveals the inner world, mood, imagination of the performer. It is this aspect that constitutes the essence of the formation of a performance style. The development of this style is a complex, multi-stage and creative process that requires an individual approach.

During the study, practical exercises were conducted with students of different ages and levels of preparation in accordion performance. One of the most important situations observed during the lessons was that, despite the student's technical capabilities, the performance expression lacked objectivity, excitement, and logicity of musical speech. This situation indicates the main problem in the formation of the performance style - the imbalance between musical thinking and technical skills.

Therefore, during the lessons, special attention was paid to the development of musical hearing, phrasing, conscious execution of articulation, breathing, and expressive construction of musical sentences. Especially effective when working on works was the systematic work on creating a musical image through performance tools such as dynamic nuances, tempo changes, and register changes. Each student was asked questions about how he could express the work with his own voice and style, and was encouraged to freely analyze it.

During the lessons, samples from classical, folk, and modern works were selected and compared in terms of style. For example, in the work "Romantic Etude" written for the accordion by A. Kussyakov, attention is paid to softness, dynamic transitions in phrases, while in folk melodies, emphasis is placed on revealing an image through rhythmic clear pronunciation and expressive articulation. This approach activated the creative thinking of the performer and taught them to "speak" musical speech.

In addition, the practice of analyzing students' own performance through audio recordings was introduced. Through this method, they learned to listen to their mistakes and analyze them consciously. The process, which initially began with simple but expressive exercises (for example, playing one note with different dynamics, alternating legato and staccato, exercises in notation), later led to the interpretation of complex works.

The results showed that in order for a student's performance to be unique, musically expressive, dramatic and meaningful, he must first understand the musical text, develop an inner musical ear and, most importantly, go on stage with confidence. This is closely related to the theoretical analysis, individual approach and creative exercises provided by the teacher.

Thus, the development of a performance style is not a simple improvement of technical skills, but a complex pedagogical and artistic process that occurs through the combination of creative thinking, musical imagination, inner voice and aesthetic views. It is these aspects that serve to understand the aesthetic

values of accordion performance in music education and the formation of the student as a musical personality.

Results.

Music is not only the art of sound, but also the language of the soul, the expression of inner experiences and artistic thinking. That is why in instrumental performance, especially in such an instrument with such a wide range of expressive possibilities as the accordion, the issue of forming a performance style goes far beyond technical skills. Based on the observations, practical exercises and analytical support conducted during the research process, the following important conclusions were drawn.

First of all, in order to develop a student's performance style, it is necessary to bring musical hearing into an active state. This is not just listening, but a process of consciously perceiving, understanding and recreating musical structure, phrase, dynamic nuances and images. This ability is formed through regular analytical work, expressive exercises under the guidance of a teacher, and exposure to works of various natures.

Secondly, technique and expression are an inseparable whole system. In many cases, students, focusing on technical complexities, neglect the spiritual and aesthetic side of music. In fact, the style of performance is a set of actions aimed at revealing the inner content and spiritual tone of music. Technique is a means to this end, not a goal.

Thirdly, individuality and independent analysis are the main factors in the formation of the style of performance. Students can interpret the same work in different ways, each expressing it based on their own inner feelings and aesthetic views. This situation requires a guiding, inspiring approach from the teacher, rather than strict control.

The results of the study show that the development of performance style skills in accordion performance directly depends not only on the correct choice of pedagogical methods, but also on the student's attitude to music, internal emotional state, stage experience and motivation. Each student must find his own voice, create his own musical expression and reach the heart of the listener through performance.

Therefore, the formation of a performance style is a process that brings the performer not just to the level of a "good player", but also to the level of a person who speaks the language of music. And the role of the teacher who manages this process is not to be a giver of knowledge, but to be a source of inspiration leading to art.

Conclusion

Instrumental performance, especially the art of the accordion, is distinguished by the richness of musical means of expression and the breadth of technical possibilities. Based on the results of this study, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. Performance style is not only a complex process consisting of technical skills, but also a combination of musical thinking, inner hearing, image creation and means of expression. Its development requires a step-by-step and systematic methodological approach.

2. In the formation of stylistic skills in accordion performance, musical analysis, intonational accuracy, phrasing, articulation, conscious use of dynamic nuances and register changes are of great importance.

3. The harmony of technique and expression is the basis of the performance style. If the student's technical maturity is not in harmony with the level of his artistic understanding of the musical text, the performance style cannot be mature.

4. Through didactic exercises, performance analysis, self-listening (audio-assisted analysis) methods, the student acquires the skills to evaluate his performance, understand his mistakes and independently correct them. This serves to strengthen the performance style.

5. The role of the teacher should be interpreted not as a controller of the performer, but as a coach who guides him in his formation as a musical personality, inspires him, and awakens stylistic freedom.

Thus, the formation of a performance style in accordion performance is a complex pedagogical, psychological and aesthetic process that serves to educate the student as an artist. The theoretical and practical recommendations put forward in this article can serve to improve the performance culture in the accordion direction in the music education system.

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